

**FORMATION OF PHYSICAL AND LABOR EDUCATION
THROUGH THE THEORY AND METHODOLOGY OF ACQUAINTANCE
WITH NATURE**

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Children's labor in nature holds significant educational importance. Through the process of labor, children's relationship with nature is shaped. Labor in nature teaches children to approach tasks with responsibility. However, for this, children must have acquired the necessary labor skills and understand the significance of their efforts. Labor in nature creates favorable conditions for the sensory education of preschool-aged children. The educator teaches children through labor to achieve goals and outcomes while considering the sensory characteristics of objects. For example, in order to determine whether a plant needs water, the child should observe its condition such as the elasticity and firmness of its leaves and stems, or whether it is wilted or soft, as well as the moisture and density of the soil. Through the labor process, children will understand that the state of plants depends on the adequacy of factors such as light, moisture, heat, and soil quality.

They will also learn that changes in the environment can affect the condition of plants. This understanding impacts their attitude toward labor, making it more conscious and goal-directed. Labor in nature fosters an interest in work and the development of a hardworking attitude. Labor in nature is one of the methods for cultivating observational skills. If observation is linked to labor, it becomes more effective. In addition to educational tasks, labor in nature also addresses teaching objectives. Through labor, children gain knowledge about the characteristics and qualities of plants, their structure, needs, main stages of growth, methods of

cultivation, and seasonal changes in their lives. Similarly, they learn about animals, their appearance, needs, movements, lifestyles, and seasonal changes. Moreover, children learn how to care for animals in nature, thereby acquiring labor skills. When introducing children to nature, organizing their labor is important. Children's labor in nature can be organized in the form of individual tasks or collective labor. Individual tasks are used for all age groups in kindergartens.

These tasks allow the educator to manage the child's actions more effectively, offer help, provide additional explanations, give advice, monitor the completion of the tasks, and oversee the child's activity. All of this contributes to the clear and steady formation of skills and abilities, as well as the development of a sense of responsibility for the assigned tasks and the habit of working diligently. Labor in nature has significant educational value. In the process of labor, children's relationship with nature is shaped. Labor in nature teaches children to approach tasks with responsibility. However, for this, children need to acquire the necessary labor skills and understand the importance of their efforts.

Labor in nature creates favorable conditions for the sensory education of preschool-aged children. The educator teaches children to achieve goals and results through labor, while also making them aware of the sensory characteristics of objects. For example, to determine if a plant needs water, children should observe its condition—such as the elasticity and firmness of its leaves and stems, or whether it is wilted or soft, as well as the moisture and density of the soil. During the labor process, children will realize that the condition of plants depends on factors such as light, moisture, heat, and soil quality. They will also learn that changes in the environment can alter the state of plants. Understanding these relationships will influence their attitude toward labor—making it more conscious and goal-oriented.

Children develop an interest in nature and a hardworking attitude. Labor in nature is one of the methods to enhance observational skills. If observation is connected to labor, it becomes more effective. In addition to its educational

functions, labor in nature also solves teaching tasks. Through labor, children learn about the characteristics and qualities of plants, their structure, needs, stages of growth, methods of cultivation, and seasonal changes in their lives. They also learn about animals—their external appearance, needs, movements, lifestyles, and seasonal changes. Furthermore, children learn how to care for animals in nature, thus acquiring labor skills. Collective labor allows the development of labor skills and abilities in all children of the group simultaneously. This form of labor is necessary for forming relationships within the group. It helps children understand the common goal of the labor, agree on tasks, coordinate their actions, plan work together, help their peers, and assess each other's efforts.

Organizing Children's Labor in Nature

Children's labor in nature can be organized in the form of individual tasks and collective labor.

Individual tasks are used for all age groups in preschool educational institutions. These tasks allow the educator to manage the child's actions more effectively: offering help, providing additional explanations, giving advice, monitoring the completion of tasks, and overseeing the child's activities. All of this helps in the clear and steady formation of skills and abilities, as well as in developing a sense of responsibility for the assigned tasks and the habit of working diligently.

Collective labor, on the other hand, provides an opportunity to develop labor skills and abilities in all children of the group simultaneously. This form of labor is essential for the formation of relationships within the group. It helps children understand the common goal of the labor, agree on tasks, coordinate their actions, plan work together, assist their peers, and evaluate each other's efforts. One of the forms of organizing children's labor is the duty roster. Children start doing duty in the nature corner in the older group. This form of labor provides an opportunity to improve labor skills and form the social aspects of labor.

Guiding Children's Labor

Small Groups:

In small groups, children participate in the educator's labor related to caring for animals and plants in the nature corner and the yard. They are assigned 1–2 individual tasks, such as preparing food for birds and placing it in the bird feeder, watering plants with pre-prepared water, and similar activities. The educator gradually involves all children in this short-term labor process.

Medium Groups:

The organization of work in the labor process for five-year-old children is similar to that of small groups. Although individual tasks play a major role, these tasks take on a long-term character. Children work on the same task for 2-3 days. As a result, the labor process becomes more complex in the medium group.

Older Groups:

In the older group, children not only need to understand labor but also learn how to demonstrate the results of their tasks, organize the sequence of tasks, select the necessary tools, and work independently (with minimal assistance from the educator).

Individual tasks related to the care of plants and animals become long-term projects.

In the older group, duty in the nature corner is introduced. When organizing the duty roster, the educator holds a session to familiarize the children with the duties of the roster, reminds them of the methods of caring for the animals living in the nature corner, and introduces new animals. At any given time, 2-3 children perform duty in the nature corner. **Choosing Children for Duty**

Children who perform well in duty are selected along with those who have not yet fully developed the necessary skills. Duty teaches children a sense of responsibility and industriousness. Children's labor in nature holds great educational importance. During the labor process, children's relationship with nature is formed. Labor in nature teaches children to approach assigned tasks with

responsibility. However, for this to happen, children must acquire the necessary labor skills and understand the significance of their work.

Labor in nature creates favorable conditions for the sensory education of preschool children. The educator teaches children to achieve goals and results through labor, while also making them aware of sensory characteristics of objects. For example, in determining if a plant needs water, children must observe its condition—such as the elasticity, firmness, or wilting of the leaves and stems, and the moisture and density of the soil.

In the labor process, children realize that a plant's condition depends on factors such as light, moisture, heat, and soil quality. They will also learn that changes in the environment can affect the condition of the plants. Understanding these relationships influences their approach to labor—making it more conscious and goal-oriented. Children develop an interest in nature and a hardworking attitude.

Labor in nature is one of the methods to enhance observation skills. If observation is connected with labor, it becomes more effective. In addition to its educational functions, labor in nature also solves teaching tasks. Through labor, children learn about the characteristics and qualities of plants, their structure, needs, stages of development, cultivation methods, and seasonal changes in plants. They also learn about animals, their external appearance, needs, movements, lifestyles, and seasonal changes. Furthermore, children learn how to care for animals in the nature corner, thereby acquiring labor skills.

Organizing Children's Labor in Nature

Children's labor in nature is organized in the form of individual tasks and collective labor. Individual tasks are used across all age groups in preschool institutions. These tasks allow the educator to manage the child's actions more effectively: offering help, providing additional explanations, giving advice, monitoring the completion of tasks, and overseeing the child's activities. All of this helps in the clear and steady formation of skills and abilities, as well as in

developing a sense of responsibility for the assigned tasks and the habit of working diligently.

Collective labor, on the other hand, provides an opportunity to develop labor skills and abilities in all children of the group simultaneously. This form of labor is essential for the formation of relationships within the group. It helps children understand the common goal of the labor, agree on tasks, coordinate their actions, plan work together, assist their peers, and evaluate each other's efforts.

REFERENCES USED:

1. "Theory and methodology of introduction to nature." 2023. Textbook
2. K.M. Jabborova. Peculiarities of environmental education for children of preschool age. T., 2009.
3. O. U. Khasanboyeva, Kh. D. Djaborova. "Methodology of introducing children to nature". T., "Cholpon" 2017.
4. Q. Haydarov. S. Nishonova. Basics of science and introducing children to nature. T., "Teacher" 1992.
- 5 P.A. Yusupova. Environmental education for preschool children. T., "Teacher" 1995.
6. K. Khoshimov and others. "History of Pedagogy". Manual. T., "Teacher" 1996.
7. O. Khasanboyeva and others. "History of Pedagogy". Manual. T., "Teacher" 1997.
8. Kh. D. Djaborova. The nature of environmental education for children of preschool age. T., "Teacher", 2000.
9. H.S Yoldoshev., Sh.M. Avazov. Basics of ecology and nature protection. Study guide. - T.: Labor, 2003.

